

Digital Financial Literacy: An Empirical Study on Millennials in India

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Abstract: In today's increasingly digital world, financial literacy has become more important than ever before. With the rise of online banking, mobile payments, and cryptocurrencies, it is crucial for individuals to have a basic understanding of financial concepts and tools to make informed decisions about their money. This paper attempts to study digital financial literacy on the components of digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control using primary data collected from 265 millennials of five cities of India. Findings revealed that there is a noteworthy difference found between digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control based on millennials' city of residence. Results also revealed the relationship between digital financial literacy components. Findings showcased that the importance of digital financial literacy cannot be overstated. With the increasing use of digital financial tools, individuals who lack financial literacy are at risk of falling victim to financial scams, making poor financial decisions, and failing to take advantage of opportunities to grow their wealth.

Keywords: Digital Financial Literacy, Digital Financial Services Knowledge, Awareness, Risk Control, Financial Literacy

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1. Introduction

Digital financial literacy refers to the "ability to understand and use digital financial tools and technologies to manage personal finances. This includes understanding basic financial

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concepts such as budgeting, saving, investing, and managing debt, as well as understanding how to use digital tools such as mobile banking apps, online investment platforms, and digital wallets.”

The economy has witnessed a rapid digital financial transformation, increasing the importance of digital financial literacy. The term Digital Financial literacy can be defined as the ability to interact with digital media platforms such as computers, mobiles, smartphones etc. to perform financial transactions electronically. The importance of digital financial literacy (DFL) in education in the digital age is anticipated to rise (Morgan et al, 2019). Similar to digital literacy and financial literacy, digital financial literacy is a multi-dimensional concept. While some previous literature (e.g., OECD 2017) described various aspects concerning digital financial literacy, there is still no standardized definition of digital financial literacy.

A person's capacity to understand, evaluates, manage, and explain a personal money concern is referred to as financial literacy. It refers to the collection of abilities and information that enables a person to do certain tasks. Through their financial knowledge, they can make well-informed and successful judgments. It is the ability to manage money by making well-informed decisions and make successful decisions about money usage and management. Digital financial literacy refers to a person's understanding of online shopping, online payment methods, and online banking. Those most vulnerable to financial exclusion are likely to be those most vulnerable to the digital transition. Financial literacy (FL) and digital literacy (DL), according to the major stakeholders, are complimentary strategies for improving everyone's standard of living and financial security (Lyons and Hanna, 2021).

Financial literacy in the digital age is critical as all financial services and products are now available in digital form, and the current administration is concentrating on a cashless and digital India. These technological advancements have become ingrained in the core services provided by financial institutions, mobile operators, and third-party providers, who now use mobile phones, point-of-sale (POS) devices, and networks of small-scale agents to provide essential financial services at a low cost and with ease. DFS innovations have also defined new institutions such as agent network managers, payment aggregators, and others to create a more expansive and efficient ecosystem. DFS can collect data that financial services companies might utilise to create solutions that are targeted to the repayment capacity and financial requirements of poor and low-income customers (Lyman and Lauer, 2015). To make successful use of fintech-enabled financial services and minimise miss-selling, frauds such as phishing, cyber assaults, unauthorised data usage, discriminatory treatment, and behavioural concerns such as excessive borrowing, better

levels of digital financial literacy are required. Financial literacy in the digital age is going to become an increasingly significant part of education.

Figure 1: Digital and Financial Literacy

Source: <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/courses/cryptocurrency-beyond-bitcoin-teach-out/0/steps/226755>

Financial literacy (FL) has long been considered a workable strategy to increase financial inclusion and lessen inequities in the financial markets (OECD, 2015). Recently, though, Florida has undergone a paradigm change towards what is now known as "digital financial literacy" (DFL). In addition to having a basic understanding of FL, people who participate in the digital economy and society also need to be able to operate digital devices like mobile phones, smartphones, and tablets, conduct digital financial transactions, and protect their interests as online shoppers (Carlin et al., 2019; Vogels and Anderson, 2019). Digital financial literacy refers to the ability to access financial services while also being able to use digital technology. Technology like internet browsers and mobile devices can aid or damage access to financial tools, depending on the user's competency. Buying and trading bitcoins would be easy for someone with advanced technological abilities. An online bank account may be difficult to access for someone with limited technological abilities. The application of financial literacy and digital literacy to enable the use of digital financial services" is what is meant by digital financial literacy. Due to the nature of the goods and risks involved, digital financial literacy therefore bridges the gap between the notions of digital literacy and financial literacy while yet having certain distinctive features.

The use of digital financial services is expanding. Globally, there were around 70.3 billion real-time payment transactions in 2020, up 41% from the previous year (ACI Universal Payments, 2021). India accounted for 20.5 billion of the 70.3 billion real-time transactions (ACI Universal Payments, 2021). In light of this, the use of digital financial services has increased recently. DFS integrates the economy by introducing ground-breaking digital financial products and services like virtual banking, Application Programme Interfaces

(APIs), alternative credit scoring mechanisms, digital lending, and others (OECD, 2018). DFS architecture, like that of a digital enterprise, is a hybrid of a financial organization's architecture and the DBE architecture. The business architecture and IT architecture of a financial institution may be described as a series of layers, such as the business role, application, application platform, and communication infrastructure. In turn, the DBE architecture describes four clusters: social, process, digital, and technological (Pashkov and Pelykh, 2021). The DFS conceptual model, displayed in the given below Figure 2, reflects the mentioned components of the digital business model and the DFS architecture.

Figure 2: The DFS conceptual model

Source: Pashkov and Pelykh (2021).

2. Literature Review

The efficient use of digital financial services requires digital financial literacy (Morgan et al., 2020). Financial customers have both possibilities and problems with digital financial services. Opportunities include individualised financial goods and services, quicker transactions, and easy access to financial products. The adoption of sophisticated technology-based financial products poses obstacles, as does handling sophistication (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2021). Technologically based solutions for financial literacy teaching have risen significantly in recent years due to the idea that they will improve on current methods. The studies presented a concept for a technology-based intervention in financial literacy education and suggested a practise and research action plan (Way and Wong, 2010). Digital literacy enhances online users' financial learning

experiences (Tiwari et al., 2020). Higher levels of digital financial literacy are necessary for the effective use of DFS (Morgan et al., 2020). Alliance for Financial Inclusion identifies Digital Financial Literacy (DFL) as a framework that integrates financial literacy, financial competence, and digital literacy.

Financial literacy and the impact of the factors that determine investing decisions are correlated, according to Arif's (2015) analysis. 154 respondents provided information for the study regarding "the demographics of the investors, variables influencing investment decisions, and the level of financial literacy of the private traders at Karachi Stock Exchange. The investigation came to the conclusion that the investors' financial literacy was below average. Regarding the age, gender, employment activity, and marital relationship of the respondents, a considerable disparity in financial literacy was discovered. In order to determine what factors can facilitate or hinder the adoption of digital financial services (DFS), Finau et al. (2016) investigated how rural residents perceived these services. Mobile network operators offer DFS, either independently or in association with commercial banks. The study discovered that agents' lack of flexibility and the implicit fees they charge customers are barriers to the uptake of DFS. Additionally, users frequently spend all of the money they receive through mobile money without using their phones to save money. In 2016, Ghaffar and Sharif looked into Pakistan's financial literacy. The study found that people with more financial literacy typically have higher savings rates. The survey discovered that adults in their middle and older years were frugal with their spending, while male respondents often had superior saving practices. Furthermore, it was discovered that respondents with high incomes concur that having a strong understanding of finance does assist them to live a financially secure existence.

The effects of three components of digital literacy on security-related online activities were examined by Park (2011): (a) familiarity with technological Internet aspects; (b) knowledge of common institutional practises; and (c) understanding of current privacy regulations. Using hierarchical regression models, data from a national sample of 419 adult online users were assessed. The findings demonstrated that user knowledge has a significant predictive impact on privacy control behaviour as demonstrated by the three separate variables. Cobla and Osei-Assibey (2018) found that the use of digital payments significantly affected the spending and saving behaviours of young people. It's crucial to consider how DFL has affected millennials' spending and saving behaviours as a result. In a study conducted by Prasad, Meghwal and Dayama (2018) conducted a study which aims to diagnose the impact of personal characteristics on digital financial literacy. According to the study's findings, awareness-raising campaigns are necessary to enlist more people in the world of digital transactions. Further, a cash transaction-oriented society like India

needs a double-edged sword, with more regulations encouraging less use of cash and more usage of digital cash on the other.

Digital financial literacy and wise financial decision-making are essential for guaranteeing economic well-being and for enhancing the financial futures of people and families (Wil and Lisley, 2022). Skills, awareness, and attitudes toward using digital technologies and digital transaction instruments might enable effective financial transactions. Therefore, it has become more important and is now seen as a must and a first step in integrating individuals into the financial system (Azeez and Akhtar, 2021). The effects of three characteristics of digital literacy on privacy-related online behaviours were studied by Park (2011): (a) familiarity with technical Internet features, (b) awareness of typical institutional practises, and (c) knowledge of current privacy policies. Data from a nationwide sample of 419 adult Internet users were analysed using hierarchical regression models. The studies demonstrated high user knowledge prediction abilities on privacy control behaviour, as represented by the three distinct dimensions. DFL is essential for improved money management. DFL is essential for the millennial generation's financial strategy since they have more exposure to the digital world. Financial literacy is one of the main drivers of a country's economic development, thus the government and other relevant authorities must ensure that DFL activities are carried out to enhance digital financial abilities, especially among the younger population (Shinu and Munavver, 2022). After an extensive literature review, this paper is designed to find out the difference between the digital financial literacy of millennials in five selected cities of India and to assess the relation between digital financial literacy components: digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control.

The following hypothesis has been framed to test to examine the objectives statistically:

- HO₁: There is no significant difference between the digital financial literacy of millennials based on the city.
- HO_{1a}: There is no significant difference between the digital financial services knowledge of millennials based on city.
- HO_{1b}: There is no significant difference between digital financial services awareness of millennials based on city.
- HO_{1c}: There is no significant difference between digital financial services risk control of millennials based on city.
- HO₂: There is no significant relationship between digital financial literacy components.

3. Methodology

In the present study, a descriptive research design has been used. The sampling method for the study is based on the purposive sampling method. The present study considers the

primary source of data. A total sample of 265 Millennials from five cities in India: Delhi, Lucknow, Jaipur, Chandigarh and Bhopal were chosen to assess digital financial literacy. For the data collection, a well-structured online questionnaire was used. The data for the present study were collected from November 2022 to February 2023. The digital financial literacy components were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from ‘strongly disagree’ (= 1) to ‘strongly agree’ (= 5). Mean, weighted average, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Pearson correlation analysis tools were applied for a meaningful explanation.

3.1. Normality of Data

Table 1 reveals that in the 12 questions asked on Digital Financial Literacy by segmenting it on digital financial services Financial Knowledge, Awareness and Risk Control the value of skewness and Kurtosis is below +/- 2. The Normality test was done using the criteria suggested by George and Mallery, 2019 which indicates that the variables with the skewness value +/- 2 and kurtosis value between +/- 2 indicate normality. Hence it can be said that data has been distributed normally.

Table 1: Normality of Data

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
				Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Knowledge of the existence of Digital Financial Services	265	3.634	1.16368	-0.226	0.15	-1.259	0.298
Understanding of Digital Financial Services	265	3.653	1.1548	-0.243	0.15	-1.228	0.298
Advantages and Disadvantages of Digital Financial Services	265	3.732	1.16121	-0.326	0.15	-1.259	0.298
Risks Associated with Digital Financial Services	265	3.672	1.18775	-0.312	0.15	-1.186	0.298
Awareness of phishing/spoofing	265	3.743	1.1391	-0.351	0.15	-1.184	0.298
Awareness of Personal data theft	265	3.766	1.11718	-0.447	0.15	-0.86	0.298
Awareness of Hacking	265	3.668	1.20412	-0.334	0.15	-1.176	0.298
Awareness of Cyber Risk	265	3.785	1.12939	-0.363	0.15	-1.279	0.298
Strong password protection	265	3.747	1.17754	-0.465	0.15	-1.043	0.298
Multi-Factor Authentication	265	3.736	1.1172	-0.268	0.15	-1.31	0.298
Data Privacy Standards And Cyber Security Protocols	265	3.604	1.17968	-0.237	0.15	-1.204	0.298
Know basic rights in case of cyber fraud/abuse	265	3.6	1.15076	-0.134	0.15	-1.364	0.298
Valid N (listwise)	265						

Source: Primary Data.

4. Conceptual framework

The fast growth of digital financial services (DFS), which promises to increase financial inclusion and personal financial management, has thrown up a new challenge: tying financial literacy (FL) to digital literacy (DL) and evaluating their combined impact on financial outcomes. Technology can only be transformational if the user has the awareness, knowledge, and skills necessary to understand how to utilise and use it to better their lives. As a result, the FL requirements for accessing and using DFS in an informed, responsible, and transformational way have been broadened to incorporate a new set of digital literacy indicators (DL). This comprises the skills, knowledge, and abilities required to efficiently access and use DFS.

FL and DL were significant contributors to the development of healthy financial habits and long-term financial security. Surprisingly, DL had a greater association than FL, stressing the necessity to redefine standard FL to include DL, as well as the need of defining and measuring DFL (Kass- Hanna et al. (2021) and Lyons and Fontes (2021). Digital Financial Literacy can be studied by considering three factors: Digital Financial Services Knowledge, Awareness and Risk Control which includes knowledge and understanding of digital financial services, advantages and disadvantages as well as the risk associated with digital financial services. We formulate the following:

Digital Financial Literacy= Digital Financial Services Knowledge + Digital Financial Services Awareness + Digital Financial Services Risk Control

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The Data Analysis have been done by classifying it into two main parts. In the first part, the digital financial literacy of millennials has been assessed city-wise by classifying it into Digital Financial Services Knowledge, Digital Financial Services Awareness and Digital Financial Services Risk Control with the help of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical tool. In the second part, the interdependencies between the digital financial literacy components: knowledge, awareness and risk control have been assessed with the help of the Pearson Correlation.

5.1. Demographic Profile of Millennial

From the given Table 2, it can be inferred that in the gender-wise classification, 56.60% of respondents were male and 43.40% of students were female. In the marital status-wise classification, 47.50% of respondents were married and 52.50% of respondents were unmarried. In the qualification-wise classification, 21.89% of respondents were qualified to school level or diploma holder, 34.71% were graduate post-graduate and 43.40% possessed professional degrees. In the occupation-wise classification, 41.50% were salaried class, 32.80% from business/profession and 25.70% in others. In the city-wise

classification, 20.00% of respondents each belong to Delhi, Lucknow, Jaipur, Chandigarh and Bhopal city.

Table 2: Demographic Profile of Respondent

Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	150	56.60
Female	115	43.40
Total	265	100%
Marital Status		
Married	126	47.50
Unmarried	139	52.50
Total	265	100%
Qualification		
School Level/Diploma	58	21.89
Graduation/Post Graduation	92	34.71
Professional Degree	115	43.40
Total	265	100%
Occupation		
Salaried	110	41.50
Business/Profession	87	32.80
Other	68	25.70
Total	265	100%
Annual Family Income		
Upto Rs. 300000	87	32.80
Rs. 300001-Rs. 600000	45	17.00
Rs. 600001-Rs. 900000	57	21.50
Above Rs. 900001	76	28.70
Total	265	100%
Type of Family		
Joint Family	105	39.62
Nuclear	160	60.38
Total	265	100%
City		
Delhi	53	20.00
Lucknow	53	20.00
Jaipur	53	20.00
Chandigarh	53	20.00
Bhopal	53	20.00
Total	265	100%

Source: Primary Data.

5.2. Digital financial literacy of millennials based on the city of millennials

In the first part, the digital financial literacy of millennials city-wise has been assessed by classifying it into Digital Financial Services Knowledge, Digital Financial Services Awareness and Digital Financial Services Risk Control with the help of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

5.3. Digital financial services knowledge of millennials based on the city of millennials.

Table 3: Digital Financial Services Knowledge

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge of the existence of Digital Financial Services	Between Groups	80.891	4	20.223	19.009	0
	Within Groups	276.604	260	1.064		
	Total	357.494	264			
Understanding of Digital Financial Services	Between Groups	73.758	4	18.44	17.227	0
	Within Groups	278.302	260	1.07		
	Total	352.06	264			
Advantages and Disadvantages of Digital Financial Services	Between Groups	69.562	4	17.391	15.787	0
	Within Groups	286.415	260	1.102		
	Total	355.977	264			
Risks Associated with Digital Financial Services	Between Groups	71.343	4	17.836	15.402	0
	Within Groups	301.094	260	1.158		
	Total	372.438	264			

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 reveals that the 'p-value is less than 0.05 in 04 out of 04 statements asked hence the null hypothesis gets rejected. It reveals that there is a significant difference between the digital financial services knowledge of millennials based on the city. Hence it can be inferred that “there is a significant difference between digital financial services knowledge of millennials based on city.”

5.4. Digital financial services awareness millennials based on the city

Table 4 reveals that the 'p-value is less than 0.05 in 04 out of 04 statements asked hence the null hypothesis gets rejected. It shows that there is a significant difference between digital financial services awareness of millennials based on the city. Hence it can be inferred that “there is a significant difference between digital financial services awareness of millennials based on city.”

Table 4: Digital Financial Services Awareness

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Awareness of phishing/spoofing	Between Groups	76.928	4	19.232	18.825	0
	Within Groups	265.623	260	1.022		
	Total	342.551	264			
Awareness of Personal data theft	Between Groups	69.608	4	17.402	17.409	0
	Within Groups	259.887	260	1		
	Total	329.494	264			
Awareness of Hacking	Between Groups	77.192	4	19.298	16.419	0
	Within Groups	305.585	260	1.175		
	Total	382.777	264			
Awareness of Cyber Risk	Between Groups	64.136	4	16.034	15.293	0
	Within Groups	272.604	260	1.048		
	Total	336.74	264			

Source: Primary Data.

5.5. Digital financial services risk control millennials based on the city

Table 5 reveals that the p-value is less than 0.05 in 04 out of 04 statements asked hence the null hypothesis gets rejected. It shows that there is a significant difference between digital financial services risk control of millennials based on city. Hence, it can be inferred that there is a significant difference between digital financial services risk control of millennials based on city.

Table 5: Digital Financial Services Risk Control

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Strong password protection	Between Groups	76.74	4	19.185	17.241	0
	Within Groups	289.321	260	1.113		
	Total	366.06	264			
Multi-Factor Authentication	Between Groups	79.208	4	19.802	20.569	0
	Within Groups	250.302	260	0.963		
	Total	329.509	264			
Data Privacy Standards And Cyber Security Protocols	Between Groups	83.283	4	20.821	19.054	0
	Within Groups	284.113	260	1.093		
	Total	367.396	264			
Know basic rights in case of cyber fraud/abuse	Between Groups	76.355	4	19.089	18.163	0
	Within Groups	273.245	260	1.051		
	Total	349.6	264			

Source: Primary Data.

5.6. Interdependencies between the digital financial literacy components: digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control

Table 6 clearly shows the mean value and standard deviation of Digital Financial Services Knowledge, Digital Financial Services Awareness and Digital Financial Services Risk Control.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
DFS Knowledge	3.6726	1.102	265
DFS Awareness	3.7406	1.104	265
DFS Risk Control	3.6717	1.086	265

Source: Primary Data

Table 7: Correlations

		DFS Knowledge	DFS Awareness	DFS Risk Control
DFS Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.966**	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0
	N	265	265	265
DFS Awareness	Pearson Correlation	.966**	1	.961**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0
	N	265	265	265
DFS Risk Control	Pearson Correlation	.960**	.961**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	
	N	265	265	265

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Primary Data.

The coefficients of correlation among the variables are shown in Table 7. Digital Financial Service Knowledge is positively related to Digital Financial Awareness ($r = 0.966, p < 0.01$) and Digital Financial Risk Control ($r = 0.960, p < 0.01$). The bivariate correlation between Digital Financial Service Awareness and Digital Financial Risk Control ($r = 0.961, p < 0.01$) is also found to be positive and highly significant.

7. Summary of Difference in Digital Financial Literacy by City

Table 8 shows the summary of the differences in Digital Financial Literacy city-wise. To analyze the difference between City and Digital Financial Literacy Analysis of Variance

(ANOVA) has been used. The summary results of the difference in Digital Financial Literacy City-Wise are shown in Table. As the 'p-value is less than 0.05 in all three segments of digital financial literacy: digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control as well as overall digital financial literacy hence it can be inferred that there is a significant difference between digital financial literacy city city-significant difference is found in digital financial service knowledge and City based on the mean score. Millennials from Delhi possess higher digital financial services knowledge than the other four millennial cities. In digital financial services awareness based on mean score millennials from Delhi possesses higher digital Financial Services Awareness than the other four cities. In digital financial services risk control based on the mean score millennials from Delhi possesses higher digital financial services risk control than the other four cities. Delhi possesses higher digital financial literacy than the other four cities in the overall digital financial literacy result also based on the mean score.

Table 8: Summary of Differences in Digital Financial Literacy by City

City	N	Mean	S.D.		d.f.	F - value	p-value
Delhi	53	4.2264	.9331	Digital Financial Services Knowledge	4	19.260	.000
Lucknow	53	3.0708	.9599		4		
Jaipur	53	4.1274	.8020		4		
Chandigarh	53	3.9717	.8487		4		
Bhopal	53	2.9623	1.1575		4		
Delhi	53	4.2736	.88016	Digital Financial Services Awareness	4	18.620	.000
Lucknow	53	3.1557	1.0368		4		
Jaipur	53	4.1934	.8613		4		
Chandigarh	53	4.0094	.9000		4		
Bhopal	53	3.0708	1.1872		4		
Delhi	53	4.2264	.93318	Digital Financial Services Risk Control	4	21.658	.000
Lucknow	53	3.0708	.9599		4		
Jaipur	53	4.1274	.80207		4		
Chandigarh	53	3.9717	.84873		4		
Bhopal	53	2.9623	1.1575		4		
Delhi	53	4.2421	.9023	Digital Financial Literacy	4	20.453	.000
Lucknow	53	3.1164	.9767		4		
Jaipur	53	4.1494	.8232		4		
Chandigarh	53	3.9686	.8591		4		
Bhopal	53	2.9984	1.1632		4		

Source: Primary Data (05% Level of Significance).

The findings of the study revealed that in the first objective significant difference has been found among millennials based on their digital financial services knowledge city-wise. A

significant difference was found among millennials based on their digital financial services awareness city-wise regarding awareness of phishing/spoofing, personal data theft, hacking and cyber risk issue while choosing a digital platform. The results from the study also reveal significant differences among digital financial services risk control city-wise. The millennials from Delhi were found sounder based on mean score overall as well as in all the three factors of digital financial literacy: knowledge, awareness and risk control in comparison with millennials from Lucknow, Jaipur, Chandigarh and Bhopal.

The result from the study also revealed that millennials in India are also concerned with issues regarding cyber threats, attacks, phishing etc while performing transactions digitally. In the second objective, the findings of the study revealed that there is a strong and positive relationship found between the digital financial literacy factors knowledge, awareness and risk control which predict that the proficiency of all three factors is necessary for the proper implementation of digital financial literacy. The result from the study also suggests that there is a need of making millennials more aware of the use of digital platforms for performing digital transactions as well as opting for financial services astutely and to impart different need-based and module-based seminars and workshops to aware of threats and frauds did digitally.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, digital financial literacy is essential in today's digital age. By understanding basic financial concepts and how to use digital financial tools, individuals can more effectively manage their finances, take advantage of opportunities to grow their wealth, and protect themselves from financial scams. It is important for individuals to take the initiative to educate themselves about digital financial concepts and tools in order to secure their financial future. The findings of the study revealed that there is a noteworthy difference found between digital financial services knowledge, awareness and risk control based on millennials city of residence. The results also revealed relationship between digital financial literacy components. Improvements in the financial system's reliability have resulted from the digitization of services and products, which have increased consumers' and businesses' access to information and enabled them to make more informed decisions that are in their best financial interests. You can't conduct business financially without knowing that someone with more expertise, having some good proficiency and having a good attitude. While increased digital financial literacy is helping people to connect with the contemporary world and gain access to improved employment prospects, but many segments of our society are either still without these benefits or are only gaining access to them at a far slower rate. The goal of digital financial education is to provide individuals with the information they need to create and stick to budgets, evaluate available digital financial platforms, plans, and services, and ultimately make

sound financial decisions. In the recent time demonetization, computerised financial advancing system, and advances in mobile connectivity on a worldwide scale all failed to improve the economic inclusion of the poor. Fortunately, there are many resources available to help individuals improve their digital financial literacy. Online courses, mobile apps, and financial blogs can all provide valuable information and guidance. In addition, many financial institutions offer educational resources to their customers, such as webinars and online tutorials.

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